

THE LINGUISTIC LANDSCAPE AS TEACHING RESOURCE IN PROFESSIONALLY ORIENTED FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Abstract. This article is devoted to the study of linguistic landscape as teaching tool in English language teaching. The article reveals that modern linguistic landscape represents the mobility of both people and linguistic artifacts. The study of the linguistic landscape focuses on the representations of language(s) in public space. The discipline «Fundamentals of Urban Linguistics» is a highly interdisciplinary research domain, grounded in a wide range of theories and disciplines (semiotics, onomastics, sociolinguistics, associative linguistics, media linguistics, linguacultural studies). Linguistic landscape elements can be considered as a promising terrain for the study of language and society.

Keywords: linguistic landscape, typography, commercial names, cultural codes, polycode texts, translanguaging, semiotics, indexicality.

Introduction. In the philosophical understanding of the world, time and space have always acted as coordinates of human existence, its most important attributes. Being in time and space, a person constantly connects the space around him with significant events both in his life and in a broader historical framework, constructs it and fills it with a certain meaning.

The designation of objects of reality by verbal signs occurs in the communicative space of society constantly and continuously, and as a result a special communicative segment is formed – an onomastic continuum (linguistic landscape). All elements of this continuum are closely interconnected and ordered into a single, structural whole with a core and peripheral zones.

The city is by its nature a generator of social, cultural and linguistic diversity. The city is an innovative field of society, a self-complicating system that increases the level of its own organization, constantly giving birth to new meanings. City residents are «the ones who hang the signs, display posters, design advertisements, write instructions and create websites. It is also people who read, attend, decipher and interpret these language displays, or at times, choose to overlook, ignore or erase them» [Shohamy & Gorter, 2009, p. 1].

All forms of human activity in the city are read as text and turn out to be an element of the urban dialogue included in various types of communication. The city, due to its multifaceted nature, is studied from the standpoint of various disciplines: geography, history, economics, ecology, sociology and cultural studies, urban planning and architecture, semiotics, philology, etc.

Main Body. Linguistic landscape is traditionally defined as «the visibility and salience of language on public and commercial signs in a given territory or region» [Landry & Bourhis, 1997, p. 25].

Linguistic landscape items «offer rich and stimulating texts on multiple levels – single words with deep meanings and shared knowledge, colorful images, sounds and moving objects and infinite creative representations. These displays shape the ecology in local, global and transnational contexts and in multiple languages» [Shohamy & Gorter, 2009, p. 1].

The linguistic landscape of a given city includes, among other things, the language of road signs, notice boards, advertising, product information, billboards, street names, commercial shop signs, façade names, posters, banners, etc.. Linguistic

landscape gives the idea of the mobility of both people and linguistic artifacts, it enables us to evaluate change over time in the construction of (linguistic) space.

In the communicative space of the city, toponymic units encode and encrypt the entire picture of the world of society in all its components, thereby creating a single information space, a single text of the culture of dialect speakers, and act as a «code of codes», serving as both a keeper and an explicator of historical and cultural information transmitted by other codes.

The discipline «Fundamentals of Urban Linguistics» in studying the city relies on various anthropocentric disciplines: semiotics, onomastics, sociolinguistics, associative linguistics, media linguistics, linguacultural studies, etc. This discipline postulates the study of the city as a special kind of created macrotext, or urbotext, with its own syncretic language, polycode composition, variable semantics, constantly replenished with new semantic shades.

The objectives of the discipline «Fundamentals of Urban Linguistics» can be set up as the following ones: 1) to reveal the concepts of «linguistic landscape», «urban discourse», «urbotext» and to establish the relationship between them; 2) to identify and describe the structural and compositional characteristics of polycode onomastic units (signs, advertising posters, banners, banners, posters, etc.); 3) to establish and describe the complex of cultural codes represented in the urban onomasticon; 4) to present the linguistic representation of communicative meanings in the speech genre of street advertisements; 5) to describe the specifics of the typography of the linguistic landscape.

Linguistic landscape research «underscores the potential for extending language learning beyond traditional classroom settings and into our everyday environments. By leveraging linguistic landscapes as valuable resources, we can offer learners a more inclusive, comprehensive, and dynamic learning experience. Through exposure to the language present in the streets we walk, the media we consume, the conversations we hear, and the signs we observe, learners gain insights

into the practical application of language in real-world contexts» [Khan, 2023, p.1082].

Linguistic landscape can be used as a perfect teaching resource and tool. Linguistic landscape of English speaking cities may form a multilingual and multimodal corpus, which can be used as rich factual teaching material for native speakers and foreign learners. A large number of public signs with different scripts, images, and color solutions provide learners with polycode authentic material for language acquisition.

Teachers can choose linguistic landscapes (different case studies) that match the level of their students as additional teaching resources. For example, in language classes «Fundamentals of Urban Linguistics», students can analyze multilingual texts on signs, the features of the combination of heterogeneous signs. Students can also learn social and cultural situations in a given area through such indicators in order to develop their communicative and sociocultural competencies.

The processes of globalization, characterized by the active expansion of economic and cultural relations, lead not only to the emergence of new objects, but also to the borrowing of foreign vocabulary, as well as the close mutual influence of languages in the nomination of these objects. The study of urbanonyms in the aspect of creative speech activity can illustrate the formation of current nominative models. Commercial nomination is an actively developing part of modern naming and the result of creative speech activity, conditioned by active linguistic processes and pragmatic intentions of the nominator.

Modern commercial names (ergonyms and pragmatonyms) represent a dynamically developing segment, which, in addition to the nominative function, has the function of verbal influence on the resident of the city. In the search for new forms of expression, nominators quite often rely on the creative potential of the constructive features of conversational dialogue, creating a new type of nominations (communicative type).

The study of linguistic landscape elements can help to identify various language codes (or translanguaging) in city names. Translanguaging serves the purpose of making names attractive and creating a positive image of a commercial object [Poplavskaja, 2022, p.596]. The analysis of onomastic units allows students to identify the most common, source languages of foreign-language elements – English, Italian and French and etc..

Thanks to the study onomastic units, it is possible to discover not only the connection between the name and society at a given stage of development, but also to come closer to identifying many of the linguistic and extralinguistic factors that influence the dynamics of names, their frequency, and the specifics of the functioning of the name in society because new names of commercial objects represent a kind of nominative cross-section that reflects the economic, social, cultural, and everyday life of society.

The symbolic precedent potential of the territory is usually concentrated around the following elements: famous personalities; natural objects or geographic features; territorial symbols and memorable places; visual components of the territorial space (architecture, street names, etc.); unique cultural and historical events (legends, myths, etc.). So the analysis of urban names can help teachers to represent a dynamically developing nominal layer.

Linguistic landscape can be used for studying semiotic landscaping the role of multimodality in discursive place-making. The terms of «indexicality» «typographic landscape» [Chernyavskaya, 2023, p.89] help to identify how to explore to the study of language and signs in urban places.

Conclusion

To sum everything up, it may be stated that linguistic landscape is an ideal teaching tool which helps to examine the language in public. Linguistic landscape reflects that that new words are continuously being invented in public spaces, hybrids and fusions of local and global varieties constantly create new ones to

communicate with people. With the help of such a teaching tool it becomes possible to discover new ways of manipulating language, new linguistic rules, new spellings, new syntax. Linguistic landscape elements provide both teachers and students with different cultural information about multilingualism.

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